

Research Article

<p>Halim Bey Jakova – Gostivari AN APOSTLE OF ALBANIANISM 1878-1927</p>			<p>History</p> <p>Keywords: Halim Bey Jakova, Albanian Uprising, First World War, Human Rights, Great Powers.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p> <p>The history of the Albanian people knows many personalities who have given their contribution for the people to enjoy freedom as a universal human right. However, within the history of each nation there are figures who, although not widely known, nevertheless, their contribution is extraordinary. Halim Bey Gostivari is one such figure whose contribution is the object of study of our paper. By providing detailed documents and information, we aim to shed light on such a personality, whose hard work and sacrifice has been an essential support in the context of the main developments in the history of the Albanian people. we hope that the paper will be an incentive for further studies in this field.</p>			

Introduction

Halim Jakova - Gostivar known as the apostle of Albanianism, was born in 1878 in the street of "Gostivarëve" (The Gostivars), in the "neighborhood of Mahmut Pasha", in Gjakova.⁹ He was the son of Yusuf and Minusha, who was the brother of Sadik of Gostivar. Halim spent his childhood in his hometown in Gjakova with his brother Sadik. Halimi completed his primary education in his hometown, while in 1905 he was a student at the American College "Robert College", in Istanbul, where he graduated in law. Halim bej Gostivari also kept the surnames "Jakova" and "Gjakova". In August of 1908, he supported Hasan bey Prishtina and the group that formed the club "Bashkimi" (Union), of the vilayet of Kosovo, based in Skopje, where his friends Hoxha Kadria, Bajram Curri, Bedri Pejani, Salih Gjuka, Nail Hyseni-Dana, Rrok Berisha, etc., joined. Initially he was a supporter of the Young Turks, as were his friends. Thus, in 1909, Halim Gostivari is evidenced united with the elite of Albanian patriots in Skopje. During this period he participated in the publication of the newspaper "Shkupi" in Skopje, which was led by Mr. Jashar Erëbara. Halim Gjakova supported other Kosovar patriots, participants in the great uprising of Kosovo in 1912. The newspaper "Shkupi", writing about this uprising, highlighted the line of commanders who took Skopje in August 1912: ‘Bajram Doklani was the first, Bajram Curri and

⁹ The name of the street came from the name of the birthplace of Halim Jakova-Gostivar's grandfather, Ibrahim, Jusuf's father who came to Gjakova from Gostivar – Polog Region, Jusufi left behind Halim and Sadik 'cit according to Hilë Lushaku, Halim Jakova-Gostivar (Architect Albanian) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012, p.128.

Halim Gostivari with five thousand rifles... ”. Halim Gostivari, who in 1911 -12 was in administrative duties in the Albanian vilayets of Kosovo and Bitola.¹⁰ At this point he was on the side of other Kosovar patriots, participants in the Great Kosovo Uprising of 1912; he was present even in the days following the Declaration of Independence in Vlora.¹¹

Historical Context

Halim Jakova – Gostivar was also on the ranks alongside the patriots of the Skopje club who were engaged in the war until the outbreak of armed uprisings. The preparation and the beginning of the uprising coincided with the campaign of the Parliamentary Elections, which the Young Turks temporarily declared, on January 15, 1912. The campaign continued until April, while in some of the Albanian territories it was postponed until May of the same year and there was an overly tense atmosphere. In the Sandzak of Prizren, the election campaign was tougher, the opposition representative Halim Gostivari lost by only one vote.¹² For these elections a telegram was sent to the 39 leaders protesting that in Reka and in some villages with small numbers, double voters appear and that some muftis were forced to sign the ballots; Kajmekami has used threatening language in order to get voters to obey his wishes; he had sent Gendarmery officers and gendarmes at the villages who openly exerted pressure on the population.¹³ Whereas through the Turkish bands, the ruling party "Itihade ve Tereki" used unconstitutional and illegal means, nevertheless, the election was required to be repeated. Whereas the Italian Consul with a letter from Gjakova, on May 19, 1912, announces: that Malësia e Hasit and Fusha e Rekës have voted for Halim bej Gostivar (Albanian patriotic MP B.S).

The government annulled the elections and as a result, the highlanders with Baba Bektashi of Has rose up, calling on the leaders of Gjakova to unite to protest against the election violations by the Government. Despite the Government's peace talks, on the evening of April 24, insurgents attacked the city and fought with troops for two days and two nights, showing extraordinary bravery. The fighting ended with the intervention of Riza Bey, who took assurance from the insurgents to stop for 10 days.¹⁴ After this period, many soldiers, drove them out of the trenches, hit the officers and took a lot of ammunition (22-23 loaded horses). Among Albanians there were 21 killed. With the eruption of the Movement in Peja, the troops were forced to go there.

From all these efforts, from the second half of May, an assembly of national forces was convened in Junik, between Peja and Gjakova, and a program was set for the further activity of the Albanian Movement. The assembly of Junik, which lasted from 21 to 25 of May, was attended by about 250 most distinguished men from all Albanian areas. The leader of the Movement was Hoxha Salih Elbasani (Salih Hida Z.I.), with him, in the Steering Committee, were Halim bej

¹⁰ “Shkupi” – daily newspaper, Thursday, 30 August, 1912, n.33

¹¹ Hilë Lushaku, cit. p. 30

¹² Богумил Храбак, Арбанашки Устанци 1912, Врање, 1975, p.208

¹³ АИИТ. Vj.12-17-1754, Supplement to the Monastery Report, May 1, 1912, No: 35; АИИТ, МРЈ and cults, Sofia, Fund 132, Political dossier No: 429, Secret report, 16/29 March 1912

¹⁴ Archive of Kosovo, Fund: Ministero degli Affari Esteri. See further (MDAE), Costa Regale, Report of the Italian Consul from Bari, 4 July 1912, sent to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Rome.

Gostivari, Jahja from Prizren, together with 5 others from Prizren.¹⁵ Under the headline “Të drejtat e Shqyptarëve” (“The Rights of Albanians”), the newspaper “Shkupi” wrote: “For the third time in Albania, guns and cannons are being fired and the blood of Albanians is being shed. What for? But what does this desolate nation of Albania beg that sheds its blood so painlessly? It does not beg, it wants nothing but its own rights. The Albanian begs to be alive, he wants to be alive and live as a person, as a nation, he wants his own language, which God has given him, he wants to have his own schools, he does not want to stay in the darkness of ignorance, he wants to keep his customs”.¹⁶ The same newspaper further continues: also the newspaper “Përlindja e Shqipniës” (“The Birth of Albania”), dated October 8, 1913, praised Halim Gostivar among the central figures of the Albanian movement, and, among others, writes: “The leaders of the vilayet of Kosovo, led by Hasan Prishtina, Isa Boletini, Bajram Curi, Elez Isufi, Qazim Lika, Sadik Rama, Halim Gostivari and many others, took up arms for the unification of Albania”,¹⁷ thus writing about the Uprising of Kosovo, highlighted the line of commanders who took Skopje in August 1912: “Bajram Deklani was the first, Bajram Curri and Halim Gostivari with five thousand rifles ...”¹⁸

However, from May 1913, Halim bej Gostivari, will be charged with tasks of professional legal character for the preparation of normative acts for the Minister of Interior so Halim together with his brother, Sadik, in January 1914, were voluntarily placed under the command of The representatives of the “International Council of Control”, who led the new Albanian state with the arrival of Prince Wied, here too Halim Gostivari engaged in security issues, serving with devotion, staying loyal to the Albanian cause.

In the London Conference in 1913, more than half of the Albanian territories were donated to Greece and Serbia. Although Albania's independence was declared on November 28, half of the Albanian population remained under Slavic rule. But again the Albanians began to organize for a general uprising. At this time the main burden for organizing the uprising fell to Isa Boletini, Bajram Curri, Elez Isufi, Ramadan Zaskoci and others. Thus began the great uprising of 1913 in Dibra and Kosovo. However, the uprisings in Kosovo and other Albanian territories continued during 1914 and 1915. The Albanian people throughout this period was subjected to the violence of unbridled terror, which for three years organized three uprisings, which shows that they did not submit.

Also, the liberation movement of Kosovo, in addition to the military wing, has had a political wing since the Albanian League of Prizren, which was also the soul of the movement. Thus the popular tribunes of the occupied Albanian part, Kosovo, were forced to continue the armed struggle for the liberation of the newly occupied lands. Therefore, in this situation, it was deemed necessary to form a political body to lead and direct this war. To meet the challenges of

¹⁵ AIHT, The Development of the Uprising-Ionian Assembly, Vienna June 20, 1912, Chief of General Staff p. No: 498, Vj.22-6-670; MDAE, No. 4027, Incoming Telegram, Belgrade, 1 August 1912

¹⁶ Zeqirja Idrizi, Polog Territory in the Albanian National Movement 1899-1913, Tetovo, 2007, p.174 Newspaper “Skopje” no. : 31, Skopje, July 16, 1912, p. 1.

¹⁷ Hil Lushaku, Halim Jakova- Gostivari (Architect of the Albanian Police) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012, p. 133.

¹⁸ Hil Lushaku, Halim Jakova- Gostivari (Architect of the Albanian Police) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012, p. 133.

the time, a group of intellectuals as early as 1914, formed a secret committee based in Durrës called the "National Party" or "National Wing". The organizers were Eshref Frashëri, lieutenant colonel Ali Shefqeti, Xhavit Leskoviku, Halim Gostivari, Rexhep Mitrovica, Sejfi Vllamasi and Sotir Peci.¹⁹ After these, Kadri Prishtina left Durrës for Shkodra and started the work for the organization of a secret national committee, this committee was joined by the initiators of Durrës, after the departure of Prince Vid from Albania. The committee was expanded with Koço Kota, Luka Salih Gjuka, Shefqet Korça and Bajram Fevziu. Members of this organization were also Muço Qulli, Doctor Fahri Gjilani, Aqif Pasha Elbasani, Bajram Curri etc. This Committee operated until the moment of the occupation of Shkodra by Montenegro, on June 27, 1915.²⁰

After a pause, the Kosovo Committee resumed its work in 1918, when Shkodra came under the jurisdiction of the Great Powers and when Hoxha Kadri Prishtina, Bajram Fevziu, Sejfi Vllamasi, Sali Nivica and Ali Shefqet received special permission from the French for the activity of the new committee under the name "National Defense of Kosovo".²¹ With the resumption of the committee, the leadership also compiled the program on the basis of which this national body-institution would be developed.

The basic program of the committee consisted of three points:

- I. To protest against the Entente States for the unification with Albania of the independent provinces of Kosovo, which included Skopje, Kumanovo, Presevo, Tetovo, Gostivar and all cities of Kosovo with their own territories as well as areas outside Kosovo such as Jeni bazaar, Rozhaja, Plava and Gucia;
- II. To protest to the Great Powers against the atrocities of the Serbian government, done until today;
- III. To elect a commission to protest and defend the rights of Kosovo before the Great Powers and outside these districts.

The chairmanship of the committee, consisting of Hoxha Kadri Prishtina-chairman,²² Qerim beg Begolli, Hysni beg Curri, Bedri Pejani, Halim Gostivari-members on December 22, 1918, based on the authorizations received from the assembly, issued the circular addressed to the Albanian population of Kosovo:

¹⁹ Academy of Sciences of Albania, Institute of History-Tirana, Institute of History-Prishtina, Committee "National Defense of Kosovo (summary of Papers), Liman Rushiti, Kachak Movement and committee' National Defense of Kosovo", Tirana, 2004, p.92.

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ Lush Culaj, Committee "National Defense of Kosovo 1918-1924", Prishtina, 1997, pp.22-23.

²² Many articles, works, studies have been written about the patriotic activity of Hoxha Kadri, Scientific Sessions have been organized, it has been written in the History of Albania, in the Albanian Encyclopedic Dictionary, in the Encyclopedic Dictionary, Toena, Tirana, 2002. A monograph by Eqber Skëndi has been published. with the title: "Hoxha Kadriu" (Kadri Prishtina), 1992.

1. Collect public assistance for the Kosovo Committee;
2. Collect statistical data on the population of Kosovo;

... representatives to be sent to the committee or a letter that we agree with... the activity of the committee regarding the unification of Kosovo with Albania and the vote of confidence in the chairmanship of the Committee.²³

Thus in 1918, when the First World War was coming to an end, Halim bej Gostivari was to be found in Shkodra and then in Durrës where a meeting of a group of intellectuals was being prepared, for the creation of the Albanian government with italophiles. Halim Gostivari was appointed head of security in the provisional pro-Italian government of Durrës. Also from 1919 in Durrës at the end of november, a meeting was held (National Wing) in which the following personalities participated: Sotir Peci, Eshref Frashëri, Salih Vuçitërni, Halim Gostivari and Sejfi Vllamasi and Abdyl Ypi (in whose house the meeting took place)²⁴. Thus Halim Gostivari from a supporter of the government of Durrës, joins the majority, backed by the British government, and with the support of Asad Toptan.²⁵ Thus, the organizers of the "National Wing", in addition to this activity with a passing in Shkodra will be ranked alongside Hoxha Kadri Prishtina in the committee of "National Defense of Kosovo", undoubtedly Halim bej Gostivari is ranked among the brave men of the nation who take the place of merit as creators of the Committee of "National Defense of Kosovo".²⁶

²³ "KMKK" Summary of Notices, pp.93-94

²⁴ Sejfi Vllamasi, Political confrontations in Albania (1897-1942), second edition, p.42.

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Liman Rushiti, The Kachak movement of the "MKK" committee, paper at the Tirana scientific symposium, 2003 pp.92-93.

Halim Gostivari was always in the line of thought and action with his friends for the implementation of the messages that the chairmanship of the Committee gave to the delegates, where it became clear that “The Government of Durrës has not taken any measures for the liberation of Kosovo, but has been very indifferent for this part of the homeland”.²⁷

It is known that at that time the Minister of Justice in the Government of Sulejman Delvina was Hoxha Kadri Prishtina, who reappointed Halim Gostivar to the position of General Director of the Police”, and then the Deputy Prefect of the Sub-Prefecture of Tirana, as soon as it was declared the administrative capital of Albania.²⁸

Halim Gostivari also performed duties during the "Koplik War", in the summer of 1920.²⁹

Thus, the activity of Halim Gostivar will be extended by the Committee "KMK", to his professional path as a legislator in the Albanian Parliament.³⁰

Halim Gostivari - Jakova MP in the Albanian Parliament

In Albania, the system of parliamentarism, although delayed and with many restrictions, begins with the creation of the first representative bodies of the independent Albanian State. Thus, the history of parliamentarism in Albania can be assessed according to several periods, which are not only related to the dates of historical events of the time, but in themselves are characterized by certain features related to the political system.

During the First World War (1914 - 1918) Albania was occupied by Greece, Italy, Serbia, Montenegro and Austria. In these circumstances, not only was the independent Albanian state practically eliminated, but also the entirety of its territories truncated by the unjust decision of the Conference of Ambassadors of 1913. Former personal secretary of Prince Vid in his personal diary wrote that “it seems that now Albania will disappear from the map forever. The country will be invaded by its old enemies and neighbors, while the Albanian nation will be extinguished. In the face of the attempts of neighboring states to swallow Albanian territories, the recovery of the independent state created by the National Assembly of Vlora in 1912 was an urgent task.

The Albanian patriotic forces began to act on this, which called for leaving behind deep provincial divisions and for unification around a joint political project that would enable the liberation of national territories and the creation of an Albanian government, this call was answered by Halim Bej Jakova - Gostivari. Thus, from December 31, 1920 until the end of 1921, the Central Administration of the Ministry is divided into these three offices: the Council Office

²⁷ Hil Lushaku, cit., p.158.

²⁸ Xheladin Shala, "The role of the Committee" MKK "in the Albanian-Serbian wars during the years 1918-1920", paper at the scientific symposium, November 2003, Tirana, p.119; Hilë Lushaku, Halim Jakova-Gostivari (Architect of the Albanian Police) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012, p.158.

²⁹ Karehman Ulqini, Shkodra and the Committee "KMK", paper at the scientific symposium, Tirana, 2003.

³⁰ Albanian legislators, Tirana: Assembly, 2005, pp.7-18

headed by Mr. Raul Fiço; Chief Secretariat with Izedin Beshiri and Civil State Directorate with Halim Gostivari.³¹

The first elections, in the spring of 1921, although held at a very inconvenient time for Albania, would create the first truly Albanian parliament, to emerge from free political elections. The establishment of a pluralistic and democratic parliament was of particular importance for the beginning of a political and democratic life and the building of state institutions. But the Albanian political class had not yet adopted this basic law of democratic governance. It was far from the spirit of keeping the debate and political struggle inside frameworks of Parliament and constitutional norms. These elections ended with the victory of the "National Wing". In the Albanian context, the victory of this nationalist political line was a proof of the empowerment of the political elite with national features.

For the election law, approved by the government on December 5, 1920, there were critical attitudes in historiography, as for the census of the election of deputies, only to those who knew the Albanian language in writing, as this excluded the poor; for determining that the voter should write the name of the deputy himself or with the help of someone, for the two-stage system, etc.³² But, in this case, it should be borne in mind that the law was adapted to the conditions and opportunities in which the Albanian society was at that time. Even, as time would prove, the opposition itself, which was very critical of this law, when it came to power, was not able to make another election law, but adopted the previous law. Sejfi Vllamasi emphasizes that, "at that time direct elections were impossible".³³

Elections were held on April 5, 1921. The one-chamber National Council began work on April 21, 1921 and continued until September 10, 1923. Pandeli Evangjeli was Chairman of the National Council during 1921, except for a short period when he became Prime Minister. Eshref Frashëri was the Chairman of the National Council, in the years 1922-1923.³⁴

Parliamentary Elections 1921-1923

1. Pandeli EVANGJELI-Chairman of the National Council, 1921; Prime Minister 1921
2. Eshref FRASHËRI - Chairman of the National Council, 1922-1923

The list of deputies of the National Council (The list also reflects the changes made during the legislature.)³⁵

³¹ Teki Selenica, Albania in 1927, L, ALBANIE in 1927, Tirana, 1928. p.33.

³² History of the Albanian People, v. III, publication of the Academy of Sciences of Albania, Institute of History, Tirana: Toena, 2007, pp.178-179; Arben Puto, Political Albania 1912-1939, Tirana: Toena, 2009, p.316.

³³ Sejfi Vllamasi, Political confrontations in Albania 1897-1942, prepared for publication by Marenglen Verli, Tirana: Neraida, 2000, p.246.

³⁴ Albanian legislators, Tirana: Assembly, 2005, pp.7-18

³⁵ Albanian Legislators (1912-2017) and Signatories of the Act of Independence, Tirana. Tirana, 2018, pp.65-66-67, Here Halim Gostivari is 24th in a row as a deputy of the National Council while in the list for replacements he was added on 22-12-1922.

Keshilli Kombëtar i dalë nga zgjedhjet e 5 prillit 1921:
(Lista përkrahore dhe ndryshimet e bëra gjatë legjislaturës)

1. Abdyl SULA	33. Iliaz VRIONI	66. Qazim DANI
2. Agathokli XHOMI	34. Irfan OHRI	67. Qazim KOCULI
3. Ahmet HASTOPALLI	35. Kapllan DELALLI	68. Qazim KOKOSHI
4. Ahmet RESULI	36. Koço TASI	69. Qemal MULLAJ
5. Ahmet ZOGU	37. Kosh RICOHE	70. Qemal VRIONI
6. Ali KËLCYRA	38. Krah THACI	71. Ramiz DACI
7. Ali KOPRENKA	39. Kristo DAKO	72. Raim BARAMETO
8. Anton BEÇA	40. Kristo FLOQI	73. Refik TOPTANI
9. Ai Giorgi FIDHTA	41. Kristo KRKA	74. Rexhep MATI
10. Avni GJILANI	42. Leonidha FRASHËRI	75. Rexhep MITROVICA
11. Bahri OMARI	43. Leonidha KOJA	76. Riza DANI
12. Bayram FEVZI	44. Loni KRISTO	77. Salih VUÇTERINI
13. Bërvush HAMDËU	45. Lajç GURAKUÇI	78. Said TOPTANI
14. Bedri PEJA	46. Lirion GJOKOMANI	79. Sefi VILMASI
15. Behshet HYTI	47. Malik BUSHATI	80. Selahudin SHKOZA
16. Bektafi CARBANI	48. Mazar KELLUÇI	81. Shëndër POJANI
17. Dimitri KACIMBRA	49. Miral FRASHËRI	82. Sotir PEÇI
18. Edhef FRASHËRI	50. Mehmet PINGULI	83. Spiro Isopo KOLEKA
19. Fan NOÇI	51. Mehmet PILKU	84. Spiro (Pilo) PAPA
20. Fazli FRASHËRI ³⁵	52. Mihai FRASHËRI	85. Stavro VINDAJ
21. Fiqiri RUSI ³⁵	53. Milo TUTULANI	86. Suljman DËLCYRA
22. Gani STRAZIMIRI	54. Mustafa KRUIJA	87. Syrja POJANI
23. Haki RROÇI	55. Mustafa MAKSIU	88. Shefqet DALIU
24. Halim GOSTIVARI	56. Ndoç PISTULLI	89. Shefqet VËRLACI
25. Hasan PRISHTINA	57. Ndoç MASDA	90. Shuk GURAKUÇI
26. Haxhi Jusuf BANKA	58. Nikolla NANA	91. Shyqiri MUFTIU
27. Hilal MOÇI	59. Osman HAKRI	92. Taq BUDA
28. Hoxha KADRI (Kadri PRISHTINA)	60. Osman MYDERRIZI	93. Tefik MIDORJA
29. Hysein VRIONI	61. Pandeli CALE	94. Tefik PRANISHTI
30. Hysein MUSHQETA	62. Pandeli EVANGJELI	95. Visarion XHUVANI
31. Ibrahim JAKOVA	63. Patuk SARAÇI	96. Xhemal BUSHATI
32. Ibrahim XHINDI	64. Petru HARTO	97. Zija TOPTANI
	65. Qemil DALA	

Deputetët sipas prefekturave

Prefektura e Beratit:	13. Xhafer YPI ³⁴	Prefektura e Kosovës:
1. Ahmet RESULI	14. Zija TOPTANI	1. Bedri PEJA ³⁴
2. Ali KOPRENKA		2. Halim GOSTIVARI ³⁵
3. Bektash ÇAKRANI	Prefektura e Elbasanit:	3. Ibrahim JAKOVA ³⁵
4. Hysein VRIONI	1. Ahmet HASTOPALLI	4. Mustafa KRUIJA
5. Llambi GOXHOMANI	2. Anton BEÇA	5. Qamil BALA ³⁴
6. Milto TUTULANI	3. Behshet HYTI	6. Qazim DANI ³²
7. Qemal MULLAJ	4. Mehdi FRASHËRI	7. Rexhep MITROVICA
8. Qemal VRIONI	5. Shefqet DALIU	
9. Spiro (Pilo) PAPA	6. Shefqet VËRLACI	Prefektura e Matit:
	7. Shyqiri MUFTIU	1. Ahmet ZOGU
	8. Taqi BUDA	2. Bajram FEVZI
Prefektura e Dibrës:		3. Syrja POJANI
1. Abdyl SULA ³¹	Prefektura e Gjirokastrës:	
2. Avni GJILANI	1. Agathokli Xhitomi	
3. Fazli FRASHËRI ³⁴	2. Ali KËLCYRA	
4. Fiqiri RUSI ³⁵	3. Bahri OMARI	
5. Gani STRAZIMIRI	4. Dhimitër KACIMBRA	
6. Hasan PRISHTINA	5. Koço TASI	
7. Hoxha KADRI (Kadri PRISHTINA)	6. Loni KRISTO	
8. Ibrahim XHINDI		

Prefektura e Gjirokastrës Zëvendësuar nga Rasim Babameto më 4 shtator 1922.	Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar më 1922	Prefektura e Durrësit Zëvendësuar nga Osman Myderrizi më 18 shtator 1922.
2. Mustafa KRUIJA Prefektura e Kosovës Zëvendësuar nga Qamil Bala më 12 shtator 1922.	9. Halim GOSTIVARI Prefektura e Kosovës Shtuar më 22.12.1922	16. Irfan OHRI Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar më 1922
3. Pandeli CALE Prefektura e Korçës Zëvendësuar nga Kristo Kirka.	10. Ibrahim JAKOVA Prefektura e Kosovës Shtuar më 22.12.1922	17. Sotir PEÇI Prefektura e Korçës Zëvendësuar nga Kolë Rodhe më 4 shtator 1922.
4. Ramiz DACI Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar ³⁵ më 1922.	11. Hoxha KADRI (Kadri PRISHTINA) Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar më 1922.	18. Bedri PEJA Prefektura e Kosovës Shtuar më 22.12.1922
5. Kristo DAKO Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar më 1922.	12. Leonidha KOJA Prefektura e Durrësit Zëvendësuar nga Visarion Xhuvani më 18 shtator 1922.	19. Mehmet PILKU Prefektura e Dibrës, zëvendësues
6. Kristo FLOQI Prefektura e Dibrës Zëvendësuar më 1922.	13. Qazim KOKOSHI Prefektura e Vlorës Zëvendësuar nga Qazim Koculi më 2 tetor 1922.	

³⁵ Betuar më 29 mars 1922.
³⁴ Betuar më 2 tetor 1922.
³⁵ Këtu "zëvendësuar" do të thotë

Conclusion

When the Albanian Islamic Community announced the secession of the Ottoman Empire from Sheikhul Islam as a result of the occupation of Istanbul, the caliphate was also closed, because it lost ties with the institutions and this was concretized in the First Congress of Albanian Muslims. The First Congress of Albanian Muslims was held in the city of Tirana on February 24, 1923³⁶ and it lasted until March 12, 1923. This congress was attended by delegates from all over Albania, one of them being Halim Gostivari, who ranks number 28, and these sectors were formed:

1. The High Sharia Council consisting of 4 persons and the Chairman of the High Sharia Council was the General Mufti of the Muslim Community of Albania.

³⁶ Gazmend Shpuza, The First Albanian Muslim Congress (1923), sanctioning the independence of the Islamic Community of Albania and the foundation of its national and contemporary development, Zani i Naltë, February 26, 2020; Drita Islame Magazine, January 201; en. Wikipedia.org> wiki> Muslim_of_alb...

2. The Jamaat Council.³⁷

Meanwhile, on June 22, 1927, a proposal was decreed which came from the council of ministers on June 16, 1927 to give a pension to the party member Halim Gostivari, who due to the services he provided for the homeland as a clerk with his seniority in the profession but also for the situation rather than the health and economic good it was going through, the government is tying a pension of 200 gold francs a month. He was a supporter of the June 1924 revolution alongside Fan Noli, Bajram Curri, etc., which made him emigrate after the return of Ahmet Zogu to power, but this did not prevent Zogu to provide him a pension, although he did not enjoy it for more than 40 days.³⁸

³⁷ The presidents of the Muslim Community of Albania from 1923-2019 are: Vehbi Dibra (1923-1929), Behexhet Shapati (1929-1942), Hafiz Sherif Lengu (1942-1945), Hafiz Musa H.Ali Basha (1945-1954), Hafiz Sulejman Myrta (1954-1966), Esat Myftija (1966-1967), Hafiz Sabri Koçi (1990-2003), Selim Muça (2004-2014), Skender Bruçaj (2014-2019), Bujar Spahiu (2019-sot).

³⁸ BulevardNewspaper, 6 September, 2020, On the retirement of H. Gostivari.

References

- Academy of Sciences of Albania, Institute of History-Tirana, Institute of History-Prishtina, Committee 'National Defense of Kosovo (summary of Papers), Liman Rushiti, Kachak Movement and committee' National Defense of Kosovo ', Tirana, 2004
- AIHT. Vj.12-17-1754, Supplement to the Monastery Report, May 1, 1912, No: 35; AIHT, MPJ and cults, Sofia, Fund 132, Political dossier No: 429, Secret report, 16/29 March 1912
- Albanian Legislators (1912-2017) and Signatories of the Act of Independence, Tirana. Tirana, 2018, p. 65-66-67, Here Halim Gostivari is 24th in a row as a deputy of the National Council while in the list for replacements he was added on 22-12-1922.
- Albanian legislators, Tirana: Assembly, 2005.
- Archive of Kosovo, Fund: Ministero degli Affari Esteri. See further (MDAE), Costa Regale, Report of the Italian Consul from Bari, 4 July 1912, sent to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Rome.
- Bulevard Newspaper, 6 September, 2020, On the retirement of H. Gostivari.
- Gazmend Shpuza, The First Albanian Muslim Congress (1923), sanctioning the independence of the Islamic Community of Albania and the foundation of its national and contemporary development, Zani i Naltë, February 26, 2020; Drita Islame Magazine, January 201; en. Wikipedia.org> wiki> Muslim_of_alb...
- Hil Lushaku, Halim Jakova- Gostivari (Architect of the Albanian Police) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012
- History of the Albanian People, v. III, publication of the Academy of Sciences of Albania, Institute of History, Tirana: Toena, 2007, p. 178-179; Arben Puto, Political Albania 1912-1939, Tirana: Toena, 2009.
- Karehman Ulqini, Shkodra and the Committee "KMK", paper at the scientific symposium, Tirana, 2003.
- Liman Rushiti, The Kachak movement of the "MKK" committee, paper at the Tirana scientific symposium, 2003.
- Lush Culaj, Committee "National Defense of Kosovo 1918-1924", Prishtina, 1997
- Sejfi Vllamasi, Political confrontations in Albania 1897-1942, prepared for publication by Marenglen Verli, Tirana: Neraida, 2000.
- Shkupi – daily newspaper, Thursday, 30 August, 1912, n.33.
- Teki Selenica, Albania in 1927, L, ALBANIE in 1927, Tirana, 1928. F. XXXIII.
- Xheladin Shala, "The role of the Committee" MKK "in the Albanian-Serbian wars during the years 1918-1920", paper at the scientific symposium, November 2003, Tirana, p. 119; Hilë Lushaku, Halim Jakova-Gostivari (Architect of the Albanian Police) 1913-1922, Tirana, 2012.
- Zeqirja Idrizi, Polog Territory in the Albanian National Movement 1899-1913, Tetovo, 2007, p.174 Newspaper "Skopje" no .: 31, Skopje, July 16, 1912.
- Богумил Храбак, Арбанашки Устанци 1912, Врање, 1975.